
Double Consciousness of Diaspora in Bharati Mukherjee's Novel *Wife*

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**Paper Received on 14-12-2022, Accepted on 25-01-2023,
Published on 27-01-23;DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.1.102**

Abstract:

Diaspora is a term related to post-colonial studies. Since the term diaspora is deeply rooted in Jewish history, it was used initially for the dispersal of Jews when they were forced into exile to Babylonia. All diasporic deliberations and diasporic fiction come to be shaded by the ideology of post-colonialism. Diasporic imagination is filled with issues related to locations, crossing borders, movements, original homes, identities and adopted homes, etc. The term 'post-colonial' conveys all parts of the colonial procedure from the earliest starting point of colonial contact. All post-colonial social orders are subject to precise or inconspicuous neo-colonial control. Bharati Mukherjee's works re-characterize diaspora, yet additionally, having been accused of depicting Indian custom and culture in a negative way to get the advantages of Americanization in recent years, the new proportion of elucidation has not yet been attempted to assess her beautiful achievements. The association of diasporic accounts transport among 'mosaic' and 'blend.'

Keywords: Diaspora, borders, identities, social order

Introduction:

Mukherjee is the writer of seven novels and two assortments of short stories, including *The Middleman* and *Other Stories*, for which she got the National Book Critics Circle Award. She has co-authored two true-to-life works with her significant other, Clark Blaise. In her fiction, her characters are discovered battling to stamp their impressions in the New World and rethinking the qualities, convictions, and missions for a personality in a quickly evolving world. Topics like distance, personality emergencies, social conflicts, etc., portray contemporary Indian fiction.

Diasporic awareness results from that sentiment of disengagement one experiences when one stays from his way of life and receives another culture. The present proposition is an endeavor to address the issue of diasporic consciousness in the fiction of Bharati Mukherjee.

Diaspora studies provide a critical perspective on the issue of cultural migration, transnationalism, and post-coloniality debates that resonate in the resurgent multicultural discussions. Multiculturalism needs to be revised to account for the complexities of race or migration. Internal migration and its inadequacy become even more apparent

when faced with delicate immigration policies and other theoretical questions of the diaspora, transnationalism, and neo-colonialism. There is a strategic value in cultivating a diasporic double consciousness. First, it offers an interstitial perspective on what it means to be a perspective that allows excessive and diverse meanings of belongingness to emerge, as well as a parasitic place where double consciousness is not synthetically dialectically resolved but enables internal criticism. At the same time, the banal question of assimilation is suspended. In India, psychological novels are recently published.

Bharati Mukherjee, Shashi Deshpande, Kamala Das, Arun Joshi, and Anita Desai are some novelists who deal with psychological characters in their novels. Sobha De, Bharati Mukherjee, Sashi Deshpande, and Salman Rushdie reveal the inner conflict in the psyche of women in a patriarchal society. In her second novel, *Wife*, Bharati Mukherjee reflects the author's mental status in many parts. Bharati Mukherjee herself comments on this in *Days and Nights in Calcutta*. A young Bengali woman could rebel by simply reading a book or refusing to fast.

Bharati Mukherjee is an Indian diasporic writer par excellence and has occupied the tallest stature in the contemporary literary era. Her writings revolve around the Indian woman exiles and their multifarious emigrant life experiences. Her second novel, *Wife*, portrays the theme of immigration and

psychological trauma in the form of a loss of identity of Dimple. Here, the protagonist serves as a symbol of the duality of culture. They split their internal identities of Indianness to create a character that would be accepted into mainstream society. They are expected to see themselves through the eyes of others. So, these immigrants live the life of a foreigner. This results in double consciousness.

Wife is the tale of a wife named Dimple who need not follow the conventional role of a wife. Bharati Mukherjee wrote *Wife* at such a moment that reflects her dark mood of bitterness against the plight of Indian women and Canada's racial hatred towards the expatriates. The novel, *Wife* portrays the split personality of the protagonist. In Mukherjee's *Wife*, Dimple, the heroine feels estranged in America, where life as a migrant gets morally wrong while economic, cultural, and social changes constrain her. Dimple Dasgupta in *Wife* is one of Mukherjee's auto anecdotal representations of her experience as an exile in Canada. Dimple belongs to a wealthy working-class Bengali group in Calcutta and is prone to read novels and film magazines. Such a tendency has helped her nullify life's cruel and frightful substances and build a sentimental inclination toward life. She dreams of marriage, and her view of marriage starts from Indian movies and magazines. She searched for a neurosurgeon to marry. Dimple is prepared to sacrifice her BA examinations and live in the dream. This

little sentimental dream drives her towards negativity and wretchedness.

The novel begins with the curious portrayal of Dimple, who "had set her heart on marrying a neurosurgeon, but her father was looking for engineers in the matrimonial ads" (3). Mukherjee has depicted the state of a typical youthful Indian lady through Dimple's desires for married life. The novelist states, "Dimple wanted a different kind of life-an apartment in Chowringhee, her hair done by Chinese girls, trips to New Market for nylon saris-so she placed her faith in neuro-surgeons and architects. She fantasized about young men with mustaches dressed in spotless white peering into opened skulls. Marriage would bring her freedom, cocktail parties on carpeted lawns, and fundraising dinners for noble charities. Marriage would bring her love" (3).

Dimple also "thought of pre-marital life as a dress rehearsal for actual living" (3) and yet, because of her conventional childhood, she envisions herself as "Sita, the ideal wife of Hindu legends" (6). Then, her father arranges a suitable man for her as her life partner. He is Amit Kumar Basu, a specialist engineer. Dimple is married to him. According to the novelist, "It was a perfect wedding. There were one hundred and five photographs to prove it was perfect" (16). After their marriage, Dimple Dasgupta becomes Dimple Basu and lives with her in-laws on the top floor of a three-story building on Dr. Sarat Banerjee Road. Dimple comprehends the

contrast between pre-marriage dreams and conjugal love. She builds up a latent opposition toward her married life. For Dimple, it is an ongoing battle inside the reinforced and enchained Dimple who aims at opportunity and love. Being brought up in an upper-middle-class environment, she has a shielded existence and represents a young lady of a customary Hindu family. Dimple is essentially timid, quiet, and compliant. 'The agency for freedom is after marriage' is imbibed in her psyche. So, she enthusiastically anticipates marriage with every one of her dreams encouraged by magazines and movies. "Marriage would bring her opportunity... Marriage would bring her adoration". (3) Considerably, Dimple is disappointed by all counts with her married life after marriage. She develops a hatred for everything: "She hated the grey cotton with red roses inside yellow circles that her mother-in-law had hung on sagging tapes against the metal bars of the windows" (20).

Amit's mother is not entirely happy with the name 'Dimple,' and she has given her a new name, 'Nandini'. This act of re-christening, though commonly prevalent in the Hindu tradition, infuriates Dimple. This is one example of when she received the first blow regarding her real identity. She doesn't like the re-christening of her mother-in-law. She tries hard to meet all the demands expected of a traditional wife in the house. In this process, she forgets her own real identity and attempts to fit in the

borrowed robes of the others. For example:

"To please her husband, Dimple took to wearing bright colors:

Reds, oranges, purples. She wore her hair in a huge bun and let a long wispy curl dangle behind each ear, like Mrs. Ghose. She even tried to imitate the way Mrs. Ghose laughed and left sentences half finished. She gave up eating her favorite hot green chilies" (Wife,42).

She feels that marriage has resulted in impoverishing her. "The magazine-fostered feelings regarding mate, matrimony, and decorated interiors gain full control over her. All of a sudden, she finds her expectations and dreams shattered. The thoughts of happiness elude her mind". (20) Amit is not the person Dimple wants as his husband. What's even worse, she discovers that she is pregnant. She wants to get rid of the vile fetus as soon as possible. Presently, she is wearing a trendy outfit. This demonstration of premature birth uncovers the appearance of savagery inside her. Dimple needs to relocate. She imagines that old things will help her to remember her terrible past. She and Amit set off on a job-hunt trip to the USA. Dimple followed Amit as Sita followed Lord Rama. In the USA, instead of showing any signs of improvement in her behavior, Dimple becomes more and more morbid:

"she was caught in the crossfire of an American communalism she couldn't understand. She felt she'd come very

close to getting killed on her third morning in America" (60).

Before coming to America, she believed that "real happiness was first in the movies or the West" (47).

To her sheer frustration, she discovers nothing that sort in Sen's apartment, where they stayed until Amit got a job. After they immigrated to America, she sees herself further evacuated, presently in a significantly more unacquainted society. Dimple finds in those Indians who encompass her further impressions of what she ought to or ought not to be. As indicated by her, Meena sen speaks of the ideal Indian lady, completely happy with her position and her way of life as a spouse and mother. Then again, Ina Mullick represents the other extreme, a confident pant-wearing lady who is resolved to live uninhibitedly. Dimple finds in herself none of the qualities of these ladies. In her dreamland, Dimple encounters both Indian and American cultures. From the outset, she couldn't process American culture in the context of her vastly established Indianness. She battled a great deal to fit into the new condition. All her endeavors to provide into the outsider culture have yet to be helpful. Consequently, she remains isolated and rootless in her dreamland. At first, Amit struggled to get a job; instead of finding emotional support, he received her malice. According to Dimple "A man without a job was not a man at all" (102). Her frustration with Amit rises manifold. Somehow Amit managed to get an

occupation, and they moved to Marsha's level in Greenwich.

Dimple longed for a wholly outfitted apartment with a wide range of apparatuses. Marsha's level resembles a fantasy work out as expected for her, and they shift to Marsha's flat in Greenwich. Dimple was dreaming of a fully furnished apartment with all sorts of appliances. Marsha's flat is like a dream come true for her. In this novel, Bharati Mukherjee deals with the theme of rootless identity. The women characters in her stories struggle to retain their identity on one side and no longer wish to continue in the traditional Indian pattern. Although they face cultural alienation, they develop a solid desire to shun the past and adapt to the present. There is a mad rush among them to become Americanized, yet the feeling of their past, their homeland, and the histories associated with this remains deep within them. Being unable to cope with the new host country, Dimple suffers from an inferiority complex. She also suffers from confusion, insomnia, tribulation, disillusionment, etc.

Amit encourages her to go out and make companions yet. Dimple is quickly losing the hang of her feeling about the real world. Remaining at home, she feels separated and turns out to be progressively discouraged. She gets lonely. She rests for the day, cooks when vital, and, as often as possible, sits in front of the TV and reads magazines. Amit consistently enquires about what she does throughout the day. He anticipates Dimple will be a decent

Bengali spouse, dealing with her home and husband. She ought to adjust to American culture without getting impacted by it. He advises her: "You are getting American, however not very American, I trust. I don't need you to resemble Mrs. Mullick and wear pants in the house" (112).

Dimple considers television as her solitary companion. It gives her a beginning and end and asks nothing from her; consequently, she is acquainted with viciousness. There was news about murder. The protagonist's brain is busy with the motion pictures and TV programs she watches. She puts some distance between herself and the natural world. She can't recognize what she watches on television. The homicides and television become "the voice of franticness" (176). Her frequent interaction with an attractive man Milt Glasser and flirting with him leads to hate Amit beyond imagination. Her attraction for Milt dissolves the bonding between her and Amit. According to Dimple, "Amit was not like Milt and Ina" (189). From the depth of her heart, she starts liking Milt: "He was the only one she could talk to. With the others, people like Amit and Ina and even Meena Sen, she talked in silence. With Milt, she could talk about all sorts of things" (191). As a result, she turns "much worse off than ever, lonelier, and more cut off from Amit." (200).

One night after watching a TV program, Dimple took Amit to the kitchen. She murders him and feels

enthralled seeing his blood-spilling corpse. She is transformed into a maniac and wounds Amit multiple times, finally liberating her from him for the supposed 'Saat Janam' idea, which contrasts sharply with a married lady's qualities in India. She murders Amit to feel American like a character in a television serial. She is a mix of two characters a Bengali spouse and an exiled Indian wife in America. Because of her mental changes, she stays desolate all through the novel. Even though her internal identity needs love and opportunity, she can't express it. Despite the way that Dimple can adjust to the new culture, as she has acknowledged new life after her marriage, however, her Indian mind inconveniences her to let it out. Having endured incredible desires that she has been creating in the new world she has entered, Dimple encounters disengagement because of the migration. Being a standard Indian lady, Dimple attempts to demonstrate her way of life as Americans do by different methods. She wears Marsha's American garments. She begins playing with Milt. Dimple accepts American permissiveness. At one phase, her Indian awareness makes her thoroughly consider these American practices of an extramarital issue as blasphemous.

Conclusion:

Dimple creates two sorts of contentions in her internal space since she has been relocated to the new world: social and mental. Not ready to adapt to her inward clash and expanding obligation, she begins looking for an occupation in America. Her significant other, Amit Basu, doesn't want his spouse to go out for employment. He needs her to remain at home for daily family unit work. This enslavement is another explanation behind Dimple to resort to the heinous crime. The last example of executing Amit is a validation of her stifled character. Dimple in Bharati Mukherjee's novel takes the extreme step of killing their husbands. This final act is the culmination of the gradual dissolution of personality.

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How to cite this article?

R.Subasaranya, "Double Consciousness of Diaspora in Bharati Mukherjee's Novel Wife"
 Research Journal Of English(RJOE)8(1),PP:103-108,2023,
 DOI:10.36993/RJOE.2023.8.1.108

Oray's Publications

Impact Factor: 6.67(SJIF) **Research Journal Of English (RJOE)** Vol-8, Issue-1, 2023

www.rjoe.org.in

An International Peer-Reviewed English Journal ISSN: 2456-2696

Indexed in: International Citation Indexing (ICI), Cite factor, International Scientific Indexing (ISI), Directory of Research Journal Indexing (DRJI) Google Scholar, Cosmos and Internet Archives.
